

Case Study ‘Biodiverse Edible City Graz’

Report on the implementation of the System Map & Leverage Points Framework

Authors: David Steinwender, Sandra Karner, Anita Thaler

[IFZ](#) - Interdisciplinary Research Centre for Technology, Work and Culture, Graz, Austria

Table of Contents

Introduction.....	2
Pre-Workshop ‘Diverse Green Spaces - Diversity in Green Spaces’.....	4
General Description	4
Results	4
1 st Workshop at ‘Transformation through Cooperation’-Conference.....	5
General Description	5
Preparation	6
Results	6
2 nd Workshop on the System Map of the Biodiverse Edible City Graz.....	9
General Description	9
Preparation	10
Results (including post-processing for the next workshop)	11
System Maps from the workshop and post-processed system maps	11
The synthesised system map.....	13
3 rd Workshop on the Leverage Points of the Biodiverse Edible City Graz.....	18
General Description	18
Preparation	18
Results	19
Leverage Points from the workshop	19
Leverage Points from post-processing steps.....	20
4 th Workshop on Monitoring, Indicators, Barriers & Opportunities of the Biodiverse Edible City Graz	28
General Description	28
Preparation	28
Results	30
ANNEX 1: List of the LC policy core group and their participation	35
ANNEX 2: List of ideas generated at workshop 1	37
ANNEX 3: List of ideas representing the BeSt concept from workshop 2.....	43
ANNEX 4: List of Examples for Leverage Points of the BeSt from workshop 3.....	46
ANNEX 5: List of identified leverage points from workshop 3.....	48
ANNEX 6: List of identified impacts for broader change from workshop 4.....	51

PLANET4B receives funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101082212.

This project is funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee.

This work has been funded by the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research, and Innovation (SERI).

Views and opinions in this document are of those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union, European Commission, the government of the United Kingdom, or the government of Switzerland. The European Union, the European Commission, the government of the United Kingdom, or the government of Switzerland cannot be held responsible for them.

Introduction

This report summarises the results of system mapping and leverage points from the intensive case study ‘Biodiverse Edible City Graz’ (BESt Graz) conducted within the [PLANET4B project](#), which aims to foster transformative change in biodiversity decision-making.

In total, 141 different stakeholders participated in a series of events related to the policy aspects of the BESt Graz initiative between December 2022 and October 2024. The following chart shows the number of stakeholders participating/being engaged in one or more of the following activities:

- Kickoff-Event on Dec 2022 (not in this report)
- Workshop at the conference „Transformation through Cooperation IV“ on food strategies and councils in June 2023 (not in this report)
- Pre-Workshop ‘Diverse Green Spaces - Diversity in Green Spaces’ in October 2023
- Expert Interviews between January and April 2024 (used for preparatory work of the workshops; not detailed in this report)
- SM/LP-Workshop 1 at the conference „Transformation through cooperation V“ on access to food and green in April 2024
- SM/LP-Workshop 2 in May 2024
- SM/LP-Workshop 3 in June 2024
- SM/LP-Workshop 4 in October 2024

Figure 1: Numbers of stakeholder and how often they engaged in activities.

Figure 2: Background of stakeholders.

Of these 141 engaged stakeholders, 20 are considered members of the “Policy Learning Community”, of

which 16 participated in the SM/LP workshop series regularly. This core group of 16 stakeholders developed the ‘system’ of the PLANET4B case study ‘Biodiverse Edible City Graz’ together with a stakeholder group called the ‘Policy Learning Community’. This learning community consisted of representatives from organizations (NGOs, CSOs, social service, research, education) as well as institutional representatives from the City of Graz in the field of in the fields of education, health, economy, social affairs, and environment, in addition to private persons (retired), who were engaged early on the topic ‘Edible City’. **A list of their attendance in workshops is provided in Annex 1.**

In contrast to the proposed process in the ‘Methodology Guide: Systems Mapping and Transformative Interventions’, some adaptations were made to work with the stakeholder group without losing focus on the topics. The following adaptations were considered necessary to engage with this very diverse stakeholder group and to gain more perspectives from them:

- narrowing down the concept of the “Biodiverse Edible City Graz” to specific subtopics, which are of interest to the participating stakeholders (bottom-up approach), since the topics were too broad to create a meaningful system map – the 1st workshop at a local conference has been conducted to identify these specific subtopics;
- adjustment of workshop specifics (suggested workflow of the workshop, type of data collection, additional inputs) to be interesting for the participants, since the proposed workshops’ concept seemed to be too abstract for the participants – the theoretical approach needed some practical aspects in order not to lose stakeholders;
- Encouraging free exchange based on predefined questions – creating a focus group-like discussion setting helped engage these different stakeholders. Each workshop was followed by post-processing of the discussions by IFZ (such as finalising the system map and identifying leverage points) and validation of these results in subsequent workshops.

Pre-Workshop ‘Diverse Green Spaces - Diversity in Green Spaces’

General Description

The first activity was held on Oct 18th 2023. The workshop "Diverse Green Spaces - Diversity in Green Spaces" was held to generate interest and recruit members for the policy LC. It occurred before the SM/LP workshop series and is therefore referred to as the “pre-workshop.” This workshop aimed to apply the concept of intersectionality in practice through the Graz case study, “Biodiverse Edible City”.

In the morning session of the workshop, a future walk on the plot of land – to be later used for the garden for the citizens LC – happened. The participants chose a role and were asked to critically examine the property as it will be in 5, 10 or 20 years. Each role had experiences of intersectionality. Potential gain and pain points have been discussed concerning usage, infrastructure, activities, (avoidance of) barriers and biodiversity.

The afternoon was more concerned with policy-level issues. Input from the City of Oslo, serving as best practice, was provided – the talk included several practical and policy examples that are implemented in Oslo regarding sustainable and inclusive food and biodiversity.

The last part of the workshop included a discussion on the question, how green spaces can be made socially inclusive (resp. addressing intersectionality) and biodiverse from the respective perspectives of specific topics, which the participating stakeholders represent – the topics were: community work, gardening, co-creative education, environmental protection, administration, social cohesion, politics, health, arts and activism.

Results

This step helped setting up the later policy LC workshop series.

1st Workshop at ‘Transformation through Cooperation’-Conference

General Description

As part of the conference “[Transformation through Cooperation V – Access to Food, Access to Green](#)” on April 20, 2024, the IFZ organized a workshop on the case study ‘Biodiverse Edible City Graz’. This conference was co-hosted by IFZ and FUG (the main organizer was the [ACT](#) association). The event was a science-society-policy dialogue and focused on various aspects of food and environmental justice, explicitly addressing the issue of access to green spaces and food.

The conference aimed to mobilize and recruit participants for the Policy Learning Community, additionally to those stakeholders who participated in a kick-off workshop in October 2023. Accordingly, IFZ and FUG specifically invited stakeholders already engaged in previous work to attend the conference at the Graz Museum.

The goal of the workshop was to break down and clarify the complex concept of a ‘Biodiverse Edible City Graz’, along with its many implementation possibilities, in collaboration with various stakeholders.

In a world café-like format, concrete ideas and examples were collected based on prepared thematic areas derived from preliminary research and conducted interviews, exploring what defines a ‘Biodiverse Edible City’. The results were then prepared as the basis for creating system maps (see Workshop 2), which focused on the individual ideas for actions developed during the workshop, rather than the entire concept of a ‘Biodiverse Edible City’.

Preparation

The IFZ team identified ten subtopics for the Biodiverse Edible City, drawing on prior knowledge and conducting interviews, and subsequently refined these topics. Despite the interconnectedness of many of the themes, each was defined in a way that allows for distinct and focused discussion. During the workshop, these subtopics were introduced with the phrase, 'The biodiverse, edible City of Graz promotes..'

1. (Awareness) education and competency building
2. Conservation of natural resources
3. Living together in diversity (cultures, generations, social groups, inclusion, etc.)
4. Biodiversity of both cultivated plants and wild animals and plants
5. Cross-sector collaboration between organizations
6. Individual physical and mental well-being
7. Gender equality
8. Healthy nutrition
9. Participation in urban development processes
10. Regional and circular economy

Results

Education and Competency Building

The focus here is on raising awareness and building competencies regarding sustainable food practices. Low-threshold offerings are emphasized, such as neighbourhood centres, city events, and educational spaces with informational signage. The need for external resources and financing to bring educational programs to institutions is highlighted. Schools, higher education, and interdisciplinary education (e.g., integrating food topics into architectural training) are crucial. Practical, sensory-based learning, such as internships with farms, is encouraged, though care should be taken not to overburden farmers. The ideas from this table call for broad public awareness campaigns, reduced legal barriers (e.g., food hygiene regulations), and the strategic use of various media to disseminate information to diverse audiences. There is a push for early childhood education, parent education on quick and healthy recipes, and food literacy in school curricula.

Conservation of Natural Resources

Ideas from this table discuss the importance of using existing resources, such as through platforms like "[Mundraub](#)," and promoting awareness of the relationship between food and natural resources. Cross-generational knowledge exchange, media campaigns on sustainable food production, and educational efforts through technology and apps are also key. The responsible management of open spaces, maintaining green corridors, and reconsidering urban planning are mentioned as essential for conserving resources. Long-term citizen involvement in planning processes is encouraged, alongside clear distinctions in building codes regarding water use.

Living Together in Diversity

Access to green spaces, edible plants, and arable land is highlighted as empowering for people of all backgrounds, enabling them to contribute their skills. The discussed ideas promote intergenerational and intercultural learning, allowing diverse individuals to share knowledge on growing and preparing food. Proper management of urban green spaces and the establishment of clear rules and mediation bodies in the event of conflicts are necessary. Ideas were also discussed regarding the balance between individual and collective use of urban spaces, as well as combining these areas with other uses, such as playgrounds,

to foster community interaction.

Biodiversity of Cultivated and Wild Plants and Animals

The use of fallow land and promoting natural overgrowth (regulated by specific rules) are encouraged, alongside less frequent mowing and the planting of wild shrubs, some of which could be edible. Spreading knowledge about biodiversity in private and educational settings, protecting trees, leaving deadwood in place, creating water biotopes, and advancing soil de-sealing are some of the measures suggested. Utilizing cemeteries as green spaces was also mentioned.

Cross-Sector Collaboration of Organizations

Collaboration between different organizations, NGOs, and institutions was highlighted as vital. Regular meetings for knowledge sharing and planning joint activities are essential, as well as engaging non-institutional stakeholders. The proposed ideas suggest creating advisory boards to ensure that perspectives from marginalized groups are included in planning processes. There is also a call for expanding awareness efforts for new forms of civic engagement in areas such as food security and urban planning.

Well-being and Food Literacy

This section touches on the importance of spaces for relaxation, especially for those without balconies, and promoting a culture of healthy eating. Schools are encouraged to offer free meals, but also to engage parents in the conversation about food responsibility. Teaching children about gut health and its connection to mental well-being is noted, as is the need for affordable healthy food options. Initiatives like banning sugary drinks in schools and public spaces are suggested, along with spaces for refugees to grow food, recognizing that economic constraints often force them to choose cheaper, less healthy options.

Gender Equality

The ideas address the need to challenge stereotypes around food, activities, and education materials, and to promote gender equality in these areas. They advocate for greater involvement of men in gardening and cooking activities, as well as quotas for women in decision-making bodies. During the discussion it was underlined that the inclusion of businesses is important to deal with questions of gender equality (regarding sustainability reporting and gender equality plans).

Healthy Nutrition

A wide range of actors—from sports clubs to schools and universities—play a role in promoting healthy nutrition. The generated ideas emphasize the need for regulation around food advertising, especially in schools, and highlights the role of influencers and public governance in shaping food choices. Gradual transformations, mainstreaming of healthy eating practices, and educational activities that encourage diverse knowledge sources are key, alongside fostering a curiosity-driven approach to learning about food.

Participation in Urban Development Processes

Involving diverse groups in city planning is essential. Identifying and recognizing green spaces owned by the city, promoting insect-friendly spaces alongside edible plants, and utilizing youth centers for idea generation and green space maintenance are some suggested strategies. Additionally, using digital tools for citizen feedback on urban design and fostering transparency in city administration are encouraged. The participants underline the aspect of integrating citizen science initiatives and experts in school programs to engage the public in identifying plants and animals in the urban environment.

Regional and Circular Economy

Local food production, composting, and waste management are critical to a sustainable city. The ideas from the participants advocate for affordable land leases for green spaces, improved waste separation systems, and support for startups focused on sustainability. Promoting local products, especially in institutional settings such as cafeterias, is another essential point, as is limiting the number of supermarkets to favour smaller, localized food systems. Using farm stores and 24/7 deposit systems could help promote local consumption. The participants call for involving specific target groups, such as migrants, consumers, and new residents, in these efforts.

List of collected ideas in ANNEX 2.

Before the system map creation started, it was clarified with the group, that the focus of the ideas was set on settlement areas and cultivatable spaces (public, private; green spaces or sealed surfaces), such as parks, other green areas, courtyards, as well as usable streets and squares, where raised beds, fruit trees/bushes, or entire gardens can be established. Other green areas not used for gardening (e.g., forests, riparian zones, protected areas) that represent “wildlife” habitats are excluded. The emphasis is on the biodiversity of cultivated plants, which should be accessible to everyone. For later reference, the term ‘cultivated nature’ will be used.

The system maps generated in the workshop were digitized in Miro afterwards. During this post-processing step, details from the workshop discussion were added, as the workshop was audio-recorded.

Preparation

The preparatory steps included the post-processing of the discussion from the 1st workshop (above). Since it was deemed necessary to narrow the focus to specific topics, the following 14 ideas, measures, and project bundles representing BeSt Graz, based on the results in Annex 2, were developed.

1. Creation and maintenance of edible landscapes within the framework of the second labor market
2. Increase in community gardens in settlements/housing estates
3. Larger, unified funding scheme for edible city initiatives
4. Low-threshold (educational) programs in various (social) institutions
5. Interdisciplinary education and practice-oriented learning in all school types & school gardens
6. Smaller, more straightforward options for organic waste disposal and composting
7. Networking: regular meetings of various associations and organizations
8. Logistics through bike couriers
9. Creation of biotopes, allowing wildlife growth (deadwood, animal-friendly architecture)
10. Goodbye to stereotypes
11. Use of platforms
12. Digital feedback options for urban planning
13. Potential guide for usable green spaces
14. Citizen science for identifying plants and animals

The full table, including the description of the ideas, is to be found in ANNEX 3.

The preparation also included the creation of a system map as an example for the participants as already mentioned above.

System Map on "biotopes"

Figure 8: system Map from the workshop.

Figure 9: Digitized post-processed System Map incl. analysis of the audio records from the workshop.

The elements of the digitized system map have been categorized differently from the outline in the guide:

- Strategies, regulations, laws, etc.
- Norms, values, self-understanding
- Actors
- Practices/activities/actions
- Resources
- Stock elements

In the workshop, they were presented as:

Which... have a direct influence on the idea or are directly influenced by it?

- ... specific actors/groups of actors (in Graz), sectors, areas of society
- ... resources, means (financial, personnel, materials, ...)
- ... strategies, objectives, guiding principles
- ... activities, actions, projects, lived practices of specific actors (in Graz)
- ... values, norms, attitudes of specific actors (in Graz)

Which... have an indirect influence on the idea or are indirectly influenced by it?

- ... actors/groups of actors (outside of Graz; also generalized)
- ... (societal) developments, circumstances, trends (specific or generalized)
- ... activities, actions, projects, lived practices (generalized)
- ... values, norms, attitudes (generalized)

The synthesised system map

Figure 10: The synthesis of the System Maps of School Gardening/Education, Community Gardens in Settlements and Biotopes (detailed version).

Figure 11: he synthesis of the System Maps of School Gardening/Education, Community Gardens in Settlements and Biotopes (simplified version).

The following paragraphs describes a synthesised version of the above shown system maps – also reflecting the discussion, which was also recorded and transcribed. This synthesis was created by IFZ, since many aspects of these different maps are interlinked within the chosen topical (= areas potentially and actually accessible for gardening) and geographical (= Graz) scope.

System Structure

The Biodiverse Edible City of Graz can be divided into two spheres ("Policy" and "Implementation"), with two dimensions overlaid: 1) three levels of scale (Micro, Meso, Macro) and 2) two perspectives (Institutional, Personal).

- The '**Policy sphere**' serves as the strategic foundation, focusing on the institutional framework for a biodiverse, edible city while also addressing the dynamics of actors (personal perspective) within this system.
- The '**Implementation sphere**' encompasses the execution of projects/activities/interventions related to the Biodiverse Edible City.

The **Macro level**, according to the SM-Framework, involves indirect factors that cannot be directly influenced by the case study of PLANET4B or the Biodiverse Edible City of Graz concerning the overall system. However, these factors shape what is possible at lower levels. The Macro level includes broad societal and geographic factors beyond the City of Graz, such as the national, federal, EU, and global scales. Key factors identified include:

- Political and institutional factors (laws, institutions) and influences (elections);
- Broadly accepted values, ideologies, fears, norms, and societal attitudes (e.g., NIMBY effect, environmental consciousness, democratic behavior, disgust toward certain insects);
- The state of the economy;
- Trends and current topics (e.g., the importance of climate and species protection);
- External resources (good practices/knowledge, finances).

The **Meso level** covers the geographic area of Graz (citywide). It can also be divided into two perspectives: institutional and personal. The institutional perspective includes political and institutional actors and frameworks (laws, guidelines, budgets, funding systems, actors, formalized working methods, time allocation). On the personal level, it involves individual factors (personal priorities, "workplace culture," personal benefits, and specific actions). The primary focus of the Meso level is on the policy sphere, although there is no strict separation from the implementation sphere.

The **Micro level** refers to smaller-scale areas and primarily concerns the implementation sphere, focusing on specific projects (e.g., a garden, an educational program) and their related aspects. Both institutional factors (actors, resources, networking, activities) and personal factors (personal commitment, gardening practices, individual attitudes) play a role here.

System Dynamics

Policy Sphere

The macro level, not directly influenced by the case study or the Biodiverse Edible City of Graz, is shaped by economic conditions and general trends. Scientific findings, social movements, and major events (extreme weather, climate, wars, pandemics) have pushed environmental issues onto the political agenda at all levels, leading to programs and policies that support the biodiverse edible city alongside the general trend toward urban gardening.

These developments also impact the meso level. In Graz, an "enabling environment" for the Biodiverse Edible City has emerged. The trend toward gardening has gained momentum, with many projects and actors involved in the topic. A new city government has introduced some supportive frameworks—though not sufficient—including incentives in administration, city infrastructure, funding systems, and laws. However, "old" structures still stabilize the dynamics, such as the administrative structure and processes, existing laws that are hard to change, limited time and personnel resources, and the city's budget, which is influenced by the economy.

The proportional representation government system in Graz (unchangeable due to constitutional status) means that opposition parties in the city parliament manage certain offices, making cross-departmental cooperation and integrated policymaking difficult. This limits the ability of individuals and groups in politics and administration to act.

Interface between Policy and Implementation Sphere

Several system elements act as links between these two spheres. On a personal level, the actions (pro or contra) of actors from both spheres are central. These actions are heavily influenced by institutional factors (time budgets, decision-making power) as well as personal motivation, shaped by personal elements (project preferences, attitudes, personal benefits). These elements, while strongly determined by external conditions, are key because they influence both the policy sphere (e.g., creating a strategy) and the implementation sphere (e.g., enabling a garden or establishing an edible park).

Institutional support is a crucial link on the institutional level. This support depends on the orientation and majorities in politics and administration. If individuals perceive personal benefits, it can be beneficial. Institutional support is essential for successful project implementation in the Biodiverse Edible City. The experience, reputation, and establishment of actors are central factors that foster institutional support, creating a positive feedback loop.

'Implementation'-Sphere

On the personal level of this sphere, the focus is on factors that affect the implementation of specific projects, such as a garden in a neighborhood. The implementation depends heavily on local circumstances, including space availability, which is regulated by law (meso level) and influenced by existing use (micro level). The local actor field includes neighbors/residents and managers responsible for the space (authorities or property management). Existing infrastructure can have positive (expansion) or negative (lock-in, lack of space, cost) effects on new edible city projects.

Individual actors and groups are shaped by external factors, expressed in their personal attitudes. These include fears, societal norms, and worldviews, influenced by the economic situation and thematic trends. As explained in the policy sphere, the topics favoring projects for the Biodiverse Edible City are currently

favorable. However, there are also regulatory and direct factors: a garden can incur costs, requiring time or willingness to hire an external service provider (increasing operating costs). Tools and other resources are necessary. If costs are not covered by individuals, funding is needed. Negative dynamics can arise from the macro level, such as increased costs and gentrification effects (Green Gentrification). However, municipal actors can influence this through legal means and spatial planning. Increased biodiversity as a result of successful BESt projects could negatively affect addressing intersectionalities.

Institutional support is again critical for successful implementation, depending on the establishment (reputation, long-term existence, experience). Horizontal and vertical networks enable mutual support, knowledge exchange, and experience sharing. However, competition exists, particularly for funding, and cannot be entirely eliminated.

Existing infrastructure, whether legally established or through guerrilla gardening, serves as a resource and reference point for future projects. Success requires personal initiative, whether in legal or informal settings, through engagement with decision-makers, networking, or creating physical spaces. Measures addressing intersectionalities are needed due to the unequal distribution of resources in society. Networking, institutional support, and the empowerment of individuals and groups are key, creating "brave spaces" for inclusive environments. A small contribution to increasing biodiversity in Graz can be achieved through pilot projects like Citizens-LC if the framework is conducive.

Policy Analysis

Cross-cutting issues are regularly introduced in various strategies, but there are few direct references to other strategies within the city's documents, particularly regarding socio-ecological cross-cutting topics. It is challenging to assess how different areas ("access to food," "access to green spaces," among others) are integratively developed and implemented across sectors based on strategic foundations. The city's development plan (STEK), as a legally binding spatial planning instrument, is the only document covering nearly all topics, including cross-cutting issues.

A hypothesis derived from the research suggests that the proportional representation system in Graz contributes to this fragmentation. Unlike non-executive councilors in Vienna, every party in Graz's city senate controls a department, meaning opposition parties are part of the government. Due to different political priorities and cooperation between the governing majority and opposition, many potential friction points exist, causing a focus on individual departments rather than cross-departmental issues. As a result, cross-cutting topics may take longer to address or remain unresolved unless urgency arises.

Conclusion for the Next Step in Leverage Points

- A generally positive, supportive environment at all levels (topics, values, etc.);
- Institutional support and favorable legal regulations and strategies as an enabling environment;
- Sufficient resources for implementation;
- Reputation, experience, and existing resources to build upon;
- Networking with various actors (from the same field and from the policy sphere);
- Willingness to act from the individuals involved.

3rd Workshop on the Leverage Points of the Biodiverse Edible City Graz

General Description

The 3rd workshop on the ‘systems mapping and transformative interventions’ workshop series took place on June 20th 2024.

At the beginning, the revised system map from Miro was presented (see results from Workshop 2). The explanation particularly focused on key actors, key elements, key resources, challenges, and possible trade-offs. Afterwards, the participants had the opportunity to review the system maps once again, and they were subsequently verified by them.

To aid the participants’ understanding of the leverage points framework, an example was created, illustrating some leverage points for BeSt Graz. For this, ChatGPT was provided with relevant information and asked to generate examples for each of the 12 leverage layers, which were then manually refined by the IFZ team.

The leverage points were mainly collected for the topic “community gardens and biotopes in settlements/housing estates.” Due to the complexity of the framework, which was challenging for the participants to grasp, the first topics consumed much of the workshop time, leaving the second round on “school gardening and nature education” very short. In addition, participants already had the opportunity to brainstorm on indicators (and monitoring) for the upcoming task

The collected leverage points from the workshop also required post-processing. The IFZ team then added details from the workshop discussion, as the session was audio-recorded.

Preparation

The preparatory steps included post-processing the system maps, along with analysing the discussions from the 1st system maps workshop (mentioned above). The system maps were digitized in Miro.

A list of leverage points examples, as described above, was created. **The example list is in ANNEX 4.** For the workshop, a handout was generated. Since the 12 levers were seen as too complex for the participants, the 4 main categories of levers have been chosen to identify leverage points. Some guiding questions were formulated:

- MATERIAL: What do we need more of, and what do we need less of in stock? Where do we need restrictions/limitations or more openness?
- PROCESSES: What organizational and logistical workflows & procedures must we change to alter stocks and flows?
- STRUCTURES: What services/programs/offerings are needed and how do they relate to each other? What regulations are required? How do we organize it?
- INTENTION/GOALS: What paradigms and systemic orientations do we need? How do we arrive at our (new) goal?

For each of these categories, the following questions have been answered:

- Indicators: Which change will become visible?
- Monitoring: How will we measure the change?

Results

Leverage Points from the workshop

Identified levers for 'community gardens and biotopes in settlements/housing estates'

Figure 12: Levers from the workshop.

Identified levers for 'school gardening and nature education'

Figure 13: Levers from the workshop.

In addition to the above collected levers, additional levers were identified, which do not directly reflect the topical and geographical scope. However, they were also saved for potential usage at a later stage.

The total list of collected leverage points of participants in ANNEX 5.

Leverage Points from post-processing steps

During the workshop discussions, some aspects were discussed, which can be used as indicators – since, neither indicators nor monitoring instruments were not directly transcribed by the participants. In the post-processing steps, the IFZ team added some indicators based on the workshop discussions and knowledge gained from the interviews and earlier workshops. These indicators, together with the lever-descriptions (= possible interventions), were proposed for the next workshop to be discussed and verified.

To generate a focus, further processing only included the system of ‘Community gardens and biotopes in settlements/housing estates’, since the topic ‘School gardening and nature education’ was considered too big (according to the ‘system map’ and ‘levers’) to cover it within the scope of time available for the policy LC. The latter topic, however, will be further continued outside the policy LC in other constellations (incl. policy LC actors). Thus, detailed leverage points only exist for the first topic.

Community gardens and biotopes in settlements/housing estates

IFZ-synthesis

The narrative of change consists of different levers.

Lever	Description of the identified lever (intervention)	Description of what will have changed.	Indicator	Monitoring
12. Constants, parameters, numbers (e.g. subsidies, taxes, norms).	The management of areas requires resources (water, spaces with suitable light and soil conditions, soil, nutrients, plants, tools/equipment, etc.). These are being funded by the City of Graz.	Funding is being increased both for each garden individually and for the total number of (new) gardens to cover the costs of resources and personnel expenses (maintenance, support, consulting). To facilitate the process, resources are also provided in the form of material contributions (e.g., soil and green waste from the municipal yard). Targeted personnel support (e.g., for	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Total amount of funding • maximum funding per garden • list of goods/materials and amounts being freely available 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Annual comparison of funding needs, actual funding disbursement, and size of the funding (meeting of administration with representatives of the garden)

		heavy work) is provided through an employment project.		
11. Size of buffer stocks, relative to flows	Biotopes and gardens in residential areas provide space for collecting rainwater and serve as infiltration areas, which are especially important during heavy rain events.	Rainwater to be used for irrigation is increasingly collected in barrels and cisterns. The removal of "unnecessary" infrastructure, such as the de-sealing of parking lots and other surfaces, creates additional infiltration/retention areas.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extent of managed areas (m²) • Retention volume (m³); • Rate of land unsealing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Annual update of a register resp. cadastral map • Annual target-actual comparison (both by Department on Green Space and Waters)
9. Length of delays, relative to rate of system change	Most gardening projects are dependent on funding due to their focus on community work. Besides (often) insufficient funding rates, the time for decision making until approval or rejection of an application, as well as the frequent need for upfront financing, play a significant role. It should also be noted that many initiatives plan on a short-term basis.	Acceleration of approval processes and funding decisions, along with clear communication and information regarding finances, contracts, and other administrative matters will be implemented in order to assure support as needed. An important reference point in this regard is the gardening year, to ensure that activities in the garden can begin in accordance with the growing season.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Duration of procedures and decisions • Clear presentation of information • Accessible and quick visibility 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Annual target-actual comparison (Regular evaluation by users/survey)
	Another crucial aspect is that usage agreements or contracts must be established between active gardeners and landowners or property managers.		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Binding nature of commitments and information 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Survey among gardens
	Additionally, allowing gardening on a new area is sometimes contingent upon the assurance of a water connection. The activation or installation of such a water		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Binding nature of commitments and information 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Survey among gardens

	connection depends on its priority status within the urban planing departments.			
7. Gain around positive feedback loops	Successful examples in Graz (and elsewhere) – as well as learning from failed practices – can help ensure the successful initiation of new gardens. Existing gardens and the desire for a garden already inspire the creation of new gardens nearby. Someone needs to tell these stories (e.g., FUG).	There is increasing public outreach sharing both success stories and stories of failure. These stories need to be prepared in a way that makes them accessible to many. An organization equipped with appropriate resources takes on this responsibility. A buddy system among community gardens is being established, in which established gardens support new ones.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of (community) gardens created based on this knowledge. • Awareness of other projects/initiatives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Annual count • Survey, discussions, network meetings
6. Structure of information flows (e.g. who was access to information)	For various needs – legal, financial, informational – project organizers require access to a range of information (potential sites, funding options, maps, expertise, contacts, etc.). This information is available in varying quality (or sometimes hard to find) and is often scattered, making it difficult for everyone to access (for example, due to complexity).	Information is increasingly made accessible in a clear and barrier-free manner. Information on legal aspects (such as construction law), on funding (deadlines, funding amounts, funding criteria, etc.) and specific services (such as mediation, process moderation) can easily be found. Decision making processes on funding, usage possibilities of areas and other find greater transparency. Existing procedures will be enhanced in doing so.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quality of information • Accessibility of information 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Annual survey, response from gardens
	In a gardening group, people participate at varying levels, which can lead to the	(Informational) barriers and hierarchies in gardens are actively dismantled. This	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accessibility of information 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Continuous reflection (By the gardening group)

	formation of (informational) barriers and hierarchies, both formal and informal.	is supported by documenting rules and ensuring that everyone has access to information.		itself.)
5. Rules of the system (incentives, constraints)	Composting on one's own property reduces the amount of waste transportation for garbage disposal, while conversely, it decreases the need for transporting compost. It is already possible to save the costs of a compost bin if one composts independently.	Composting in the (residential community) garden as a substitute for the compost bin is on the rise and saves households a small amount of money.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Resolution by the municipal council • Ratio of compost bins to organic waste bins. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Annual report on implementation. • Annual evaluation of applications (excluding organic waste bins).
	The type of land management is largely unregulated, except for a few legal provisions, primarily at the national and state levels. On land owned by the city, management can be changed very quickly. However, the introduction of regulations for private lands, especially on cultivation practices, is hardly possible – especially if it does not have any security, health and environmental implications.	The introduction of guidelines for de-sealing and subsequently managing areas in a nature-friendly or biotope manner leads to an increase in the number of de-sealed or nature-friendly managed areas. The house rules will be adapted to permit gardening and to mandate nature-friendly practices. Information on what is considered nature-friendly (e.g., suitable plants, wildlife needs) will be provided. Certain measures receive funding. Awards will be established to honour activities.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extent of managed areas (m²) • Number of house rules meeting specific criteria 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Annual update of a register. • Annual target-actual comparison • Continuously reported house rules.
	The garden as a commons: According to Elinor Ostrom, it is beneficial for a gardening group to collectively define rules, control	Garden initiatives rules, monitoring, and sanction mechanisms are not only managed informally but are also	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Codified rulebook 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Continuous reflection (By the gardening group itself.)

	mechanisms, and sanctions to ensure successful joint management.	developed and documented collaboratively. There is a collection of good and bad practices along with advisory support on the subject. This leads to a decreasing number of complaints within the garden group resp. to a higher number of gardens/garden groups not struggling on certain issues.		
4. Power to change system structure or self-organize	The outsourcing of the gardening department from the City Administration to the Holding Graz (the city owned municipal service company) has introduced a model for mutual accounting of services. This sometimes leads to redundancies, long (communication) pathways, and occasional confusion regarding the responsibilities of the Department for Green Spaces and Water. In addition, many green spaces owned by the city are managed by Holding Graz – thus, they need to be involved in decision processes, which might take some time. This happened to the green area, where the Citizens LC has been implemented.	A new organizational structure between the Department for Green Spaces and Water and the gardeners of the Holding is being introduced to reduce these complexities. This will also lead to quicker decision making (see lever 9).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Process efficiency 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Survey among gardeners
	The exchange between individual gardening initiatives is important for their further development and to form an interest group	To improve the quality of support and enhance the intensity of exchanges (which allows for early identification of	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presence of a support office • Resource allocation of the 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Annual target-actual comparison • Ongoing update of

	to jointly improve conditions. The gardens are interconnected and networked with actors from other sectors as well as with the administration. Networks often require management. The FUG serves as an appropriate organization for this purpose. In the City of Graz, there is a contact person in the Department for Green Spaces and Water.	needs), a support office (hub) with enough personal and financial resource is being established as an interface between the administration and the grassroots (garden initiatives). This office will also focus on supporting and networking garden initiatives and actors from other sectors.	support office relative to demand <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of network members and activities • Number of connections (contacts) within the network 	contact database <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Survey among initiatives
	In the gardens themselves, a modular approach is recommended to allow for adjustments. This pertains to both the organizational structure (e.g., group rules, roles, etc.) and the garden infrastructure (growing step-by-step, options for deconstruction, flexibility).	New gardening initiatives are planned and established with a modular infrastructure. They grow step-by-step. Existing initiatives can also be adapted accordingly. There are advisory options available for the organizational structure as well.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of modularly implemented gardens. • Development history of the garden • Group organization in the garden over time (e.g., changing roles) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Survey among initiatives
3. Goals of the system	Community gardens in residential areas are part of an edible city and are strategically promoted with the aim of enabling city residents to garden in an easy and accessible manner.	Community gardens in residential areas will be implemented as measure of the "Edible City" initiative within the upcoming Sustainable Food and Agriculture strategy of the City of Graz as within the biodiversity strategy of the City of Graz, along with principles for nature-friendly/organic management.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Target values for budget/funding (€), managed area (m²), number of gardens, number of participants • Measure anchored in the mentioned strategies as well as in the Urban Development Concept (STEK) • Biodiversity (diversity) of cultivated plants and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Annual target-actual comparison • Annual implementation report (both by City administration)
	Nature-friendly management of green spaces and the promotion of biodiversity in the city are key principles of an edible city.			

			<p>observed wild plants/animals</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Quantity of produced food 	
<p>2. Paradigm underpinning the system (its goals, structure, rules, delays, and parameters)</p>	<p>Social gardening in community gardens in residential areas represents a socio-ecological thematic/sectoral cross-section. It contributes, among other things, to health promotion, (awareness) education, addressing (multiple) discrimination, inclusion, and food production. Additionally, these gardens—like biotopes—fulfil an ecological function. Access to gardening opportunities is facilitated for everyone in the spirit of food and environmental justice.</p>	<p>The role of community gardens in residential areas, alongside their function as social spaces, is changing in the minds of residents and stakeholders (as described on the left). The creation of biotopes and biodiverse green spaces, as well as community gardens in settlements/housing estates, is receiving central priority in urban development, city planning, and building planning. The city becomes biophilic.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of people who agree with the statements or act and live accordingly 1st stage integration of criteria in planning processes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Survey

4th Workshop on Monitoring, Indicators, Barriers & Opportunities of the Biodiverse Edible City Graz

General Description

The 4th workshop took place on October 29th 2024. In the first part, we focussed on the leverage points discussion in the last workshop. The proposed, rephrased levers have been presented, followed by the possibility to rephrase them. Afterwards, the indicators and monitoring instruments were discussed, some of which were proposed by the IFZ team based on post-processing activities from the last workshop.

In the second part of the workshop, we had a discussion on opportunities and barriers for broader change regarding 'community gardens and biotopes in settlements/housing estates', assuming that this intervention – as a proposed outcome from the policy LC workshops – will become one of the key measures of the upcoming "Sustainable Food and Agriculture" strategy from the City of Graz. The participants could choose the broader impact on one of these suggested systems or on others they had in mind:

- Health
- Education
- Culture
- Work, economy, tourism
- Living together/community
- Addressing special needs and intersectionalities
- Nature, biodiversity and other ecological aspects
- City Development

Preparation

As part of the post-processing of the last workshop, the brainstormed levers have been re-formulated and complemented and some indicators of the proposed levers and monitoring instruments have been added based on previous IFZ research and evaluation of the audio recording of the discussion (see results from the previous workshop, above).

To initiate the discussion on broader impact, IFZ also compiled a brief list of examples, which was informed by discussions from the previous workshop and IFZ's research.

Impact on	Description of either positive (+) or negative (-) impact by implementing more community gardens and biotopes in settlements / housing estates.	
Biodiversity	+	An expansion of nature-friendly managed garden areas and biotopes, combined with secure management, appropriate design, and the use of climate- and site-adapted cultivated and wild varieties, leads to an increase in biodiversity.
Addressing intersectionalities: of women*	+/-	Gardens are being established as empowering spaces, known as "Brave Spaces," for women, and the number of such gardens is on the rise. However, gardens in residential areas do not necessarily have to establish themselves as open and women's spaces. There is a risk that such concepts may not be feasible in specific locations.
Living	+	The expansion of residential gardens can also have negative, unintended trade-offs:

together/co mmunity	<p>1. Managing these areas requires a time commitment, which can sometimes be outsourced professionally, potentially leading to increased operating costs.</p> <p>2. A "healthy" or "pleasant" living environment (greenery, balconies, etc.) can result in rising rents, gentrification of neighbourhoods, and the displacement of specific population groups (green gentrification).</p>
------------------------	--

The same was done in order to start discussion on chances and barriers.

Factor / Aspect	<i>What external factors influence (either support [+] or hinder [-]) the widespread availability of supported residential gardens? In what ways?</i>	
Green education and school gardens	+	Increased awareness and knowledge about the importance and management of gardens and biotopes, conveyed through schools, raises interest and supports the successful implementation of residential gardens. Parents are reached through their children. Gardens are also perceived as social and democratic spaces.
Specific development	+	The stronger the trend, the higher the likelihood of success: The general trend towards urban gardening, along with the desire for green spaces and the opportunity to grow one's own food, benefits the initiative as a whole.
Norms, attitudes, values, self-understanding	-	The greater the resistance, the lower the success: Implementation heavily depends on the attitudes of stakeholders. Dissenting neighbors or property management (as mentioned above) towards a project or its direction (e.g., type of management, costs) can hinder or even prevent it. This resistance can also multiply and reverse the overall positive trend. Decision-makers in administration (or politics) may have personal biases and can block initiatives within their scope of authority (e.g., permits, processing times, funding, regulations, etc.). Attitudes and values can also negatively impact the internal dynamics of the garden group if a common ground cannot be found. However, a positive pro-attitude can also prevail.
Resources	+	The success of gardens depends on the availability of various resources, including financial resources, operating supplies, suitable space, and knowledge and experience. These resources can be provided privately or publicly. In any case, they are necessary. It is often easier to build upon existing resources (or they are more likely to be supported) than to establish something new. Attention should be paid to lock-ins/path dependencies.
Sectors	+	The greater the cross-sectoral collaboration, the higher the likelihood of success: Since urban gardening, especially in residential areas, serves as an intersection, it can address and connect various sectors, thereby leveraging synergies, such as in political objectives.
Sectors	-	The more significant the cross-sectoral overlap, the lower the likelihood of success: In various sectors—or urban departments—there can be competition (e.g., regarding land use, jurisdiction, political positioning), contradictions or conflicts (e.g., in objectives), or asynchronies (e.g., in priorities and processes), which can hinder the initiative.
practices	-	The more established the practices continue, the lower the likelihood of success: A formalized commitment from the political side is needed, along with simplifications and stronger collaboration from the administration, and a higher level of professionalism from the gardeners (or garden coordinators or support staff).

Results

Identified impacts on broader change, opportunities and barriers for increasing numbers of 'community gardens and biotopes in settlements/housing estates'

Figure 14: Onion diagram on impact on broader change (blue), opportunities (green) and barriers (orange) embedded in the underlining system map (yellow). The eight sectors represent the different systems (names in coloured circles).

(The high-resolution maps are attached as JPG resp. PDF.)

Impacts on broader change through increasing numbers of ‘community gardens and biotopes in settlements/housing estates’

Based on the onion diagram presented above, a discussion took place outlining the interconnectedness of these individual aspects. Thus, the impact can be observed not only for a specific system but also for multiple systems simultaneously, concluding that these broad, interlinked, and multi-scalar impacts create numerous benefits.

The following descriptions of impact have been generated (formulated) by the IFZ-team based on the collected ideas on impact as well as the analysis of the audio-recorded discussions from the workshop. The developed stories are linked to the pre-formulated system, which they impact. As part of the verification process following the workshop, these stories were shared with participants in the protocol, along with a question regarding their agreement or disagreement.

<i>Description of either positive (+) or negative (-) impact by implementing more community gardens and biotopes in settlements / housing estates.</i>	<i>Impact on</i>
<p data-bbox="192 933 215 957">+</p> <p data-bbox="259 560 1619 1002">Improving the access to healthy and fresh food for all by fostering community engagement and promoting sustainable practices. By creating community gardens nearby the residents’ homes, residents can cultivate their own fruits and vegetables, ensuring a steady supply of fresh produce. Workshops on sustainable nutrition and gardening equip individuals with the knowledge and skills to grow their own food, fostering healthier eating habits. Moreover, involving individuals with diverse backgrounds enhances the exchange of gardening knowledge, enriching the community’s expertise. Initiatives focused on accessibility, such as low-threshold educational offerings, ensure that even marginalized groups can participate. By prioritizing local biodiversity and organic practices, these gardens not only provide nutritious food but also contribute to the preservation of environmental health. The consumption of fresh fruits and vegetables supports better physical health, reduces the risk of chronic diseases, and improves mental well-being through the therapeutic benefits of gardening.</p>	<ul data-bbox="1630 560 2069 758" style="list-style-type: none"> • Health • Education • Living together/community • Addressing special needs and intersectionalities
<p data-bbox="192 1425 215 1449">+</p> <p data-bbox="259 1007 1619 1453">Increasing awareness of environmental issues, knowledge on nature and food and skills to produce and prepare food: Community gardens serve as vital educational platforms, allowing participants to learn about the ecosystem and the importance of biodiversity. By engaging in hands-on gardening, individuals gain practical skills in growing and harvesting food, which empowers them to make informed choices about their consumption. Workshops focused on sustainable practices, such as organic gardening and composting, not only provide essential skills for food production but also raise awareness about the environmental impacts of conventional agriculture. This knowledge fosters a deeper understanding of how personal choices affect the planet, encouraging individuals to adopt more sustainable lifestyles. Furthermore, as community members share their experiences and expertise, a culture of collective learning emerges, strengthening community bonds. Overall, enhancing awareness and skills related to nature and food production leads to more environmentally conscious behaviours and contributes to the development of resilient, sustainable communities.</p>	<ul data-bbox="1630 1007 2069 1204" style="list-style-type: none"> • Education • Health • Culture • Nature, biodiversity and other ecological aspects

Description of either positive (+) or negative (-) impact by implementing more community gardens and biotopes in settlements / housing estates.	Impact on
<p data-bbox="197 563 219 587">+</p> <p data-bbox="264 228 1608 595">Improving environmental quality and biodiversity: These gardens contribute to urban greening, enhancing air quality by absorbing pollutants and producing oxygen. By incorporating native plants and biodiversity, they create habitats for various species, promoting ecological balance. Sustainable gardening practices, such as composting and organic farming, reduce the need for chemical fertilizers and pesticides, minimizing soil and water contamination. This shift will also influence consumer choices, thereby impacting agricultural practices in general. Furthermore, community gardens help manage stormwater by allowing rainwater to infiltrate the ground, reducing runoff and flooding. As residents become more engaged with their environment through gardening, they develop a greater appreciation for nature and its importance, fostering a collective commitment to sustainability. Ultimately, these efforts lead to healthier ecosystems and improved quality of life for all community members.</p>	<ul data-bbox="1637 228 2047 467" style="list-style-type: none"> • Nature, biodiversity and other ecological aspects • Health • Addressing special needs and intersectionalities • City Development
<p data-bbox="197 978 219 1002">+</p> <p data-bbox="264 603 1608 997">Providing economic opportunities: Community gardens can serve as platforms for small-scale food production, allowing individuals to sell and or share fresh produce, herbs, and value-added products like jams or pickles at local markets. This strengthens the local economy and neighbourhood networks and allows local entrepreneurship and the creation of jobs within neighbourhoods. Additionally, community gardens contribute to job training programs, equipping individuals with skills in agriculture, horticulture, and business management. This enhances employability, particularly for marginalized groups, ultimately contributing to the community's economic resilience and sustainability. Moreover, community gardens can attract tourism and local events, generating revenue through workshops, farm-to-table dinners, and educational programs. By creating spaces for social enterprises, such as co-operatives or community-supported agriculture (CSA) programs, these initiatives empower residents to take control of their food sources while fostering community bonds.</p>	<ul data-bbox="1637 603 2047 802" style="list-style-type: none"> • Work, economy, tourism • Living together/community • Addressing special needs and intersectionalities • Education

The list of items, originally created by the participants, to describe the broader change and which was the basis of the stories in the table above is to be found in ANNEX 6.

Three of these four impacts above have been discussed in regard to barriers and opportunities to generate broader change by implementing more community gardens and biotopes in settlements / housing estates.

<i>Impact on</i>	<i>opportunities</i>	<i>barriers</i>
<p>Increasing awareness of environmental issues, knowledge on nature and food and skills to produce and prepare food</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Opportunities for participatory learning: Low-threshold, non-directive educational offerings in public spaces provide a way to go beyond mere knowledge transfer. Such settings can particularly engage people who face barriers with traditional educational options. • Integration of sustainability education: These offerings can connect with school-based learning, particularly in sustainability education, enabling children and parents to apply their knowledge in their daily lives and implement it within their communities. This also supports the new curricula's goals for multi-perspective and social learning. • Career orientation through practical examples: In projects like community gardens, children and young people can gain practical insights into professions by working with skilled professionals (e.g., plumbers). This encourages exploration and motivation for vocational training by making role models and hands-on activities accessible. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Systemic barriers in the education system: The formal education system is highly regulated structurally and financially, making it difficult to implement flexible educational offerings in public spaces. There is also a lack of clear responsibilities and limited personnel resources for low- threshold, extracurricular educational projects. • Planning challenges for open educational offerings: Educational projects in public spaces, such as community gardens in settlements, are challenging to plan, as participation is voluntary and attendance can vary, making it difficult to implement these concepts effectively.
<p>Improving environmental quality and biodiversity – connected to urban development</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Positive aspects of green space design: Making better use of the existing green spaces in Graz, ideally supported by building regulations, would enhance the city. Rather than having each new residential complex with small, often unused green areas or playgrounds, larger, shared green spaces could provide a more appealing recreational area for everyone. Such spaces could serve various functions and be used more effectively. • Vacant properties: The issue of vacancy was however not further discussed. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A significant challenge lies in property ownership structures, such as private or developer ownership, which makes flexible use of green spaces difficult. Additionally, given Graz's growth and the increasing demand for housing, repurposing land could lead to higher housing costs.

<i>Impact on</i>	<i>opportunities</i>	<i>barriers</i>
Providing economic opportunities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Benefits of community gardens in urban development areas: It was proposed to incorporate community gardens into the planning of new urban areas. Such gardens promote the well-being and health of residents, provide access to fresh food, contribute to climate resilience and climate adaptation, and improve water evaporation and absorption. • Economic advantages: Additionally, these gardens could offer economic benefits for the city if used commercially, for example, as market gardens. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nothing mentioned

ANNEX 1: List of the LC policy core group and their participation

				Living Lab Conceptualisation Events		Policy LC Recruitment SM & LP Workshops				
Stakeholder-ID	Actor Group	Specification	Personal Details (according to D3.1)	Kickoff Workshop Dec 22	TDK 4	Pre- Workshop Oct 23	Work- shop 1 (TDK 5)	Work- shop 2	Work- shop 3	Work- shop 4
4	NGO	Diversity & intersectionality	Female, 50-60 Y, handicapped		yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
13	City Administration	Integration		yes	yes		yes	yes		yes
23	private	Health			yes		yes	yes	yes	yes
24	CSO	Environment			yes		yes	yes	yes	yes
29	Education & research	Environment		yes	yes	yes		yes		yes
5	NGO	Environment	Female, 40-50 Y	yes		yes			yes	yes
12	Social Service Enterprise	Social Sector	Male, 40-50 Y	yes	yes	yes				yes
28	Research	Environment			yes		yes	yes		yes
30	NGO	Environment		yes		yes	yes	yes		
1	City Administration	Green spaces	Female, 40-50 Y			yes		yes		
3	City Administration	Citizen engagement	Male, 50-60 Y	yes		yes				
7	CSO	Arts	Female, 50-60 Y	yes		yes	yes			
8	CSO	Urban gardening	Female 60-70 Y	yes	yes	yes				
25	private	Diversity&intersectionality					yes	yes	yes	
6	Education & research	Environment	Male, 20-30 Y	yes		yes				
14	City Administration	Green spaces		yes						
26	CSO	Environment						yes	yes	
27	private	Economy						yes	yes	
31	private	Economy					yes	Yes		
32	private	no category					yes	yes		

ANNEX 2: List of ideas generated at workshop 1

1) (Awareness) Education, Competence Building

- Low-threshold offers brought to the people, such as:
 - Neighbourhood centres
 - Events by the City of Graz
 - Senior centres (e.g., Nurse Community & Jugend am Werk)
 - Influencers
 - Educational spaces with informational signs
- This requires external offers and/or financial and time resources to bring events and information to various institutions.
- Institutional anchoring of school gardens is important (with regard to priority and responsibility).
- Cross-disciplinary education in schools and higher education institutions, as well as integration into pedagogical training and other disciplines (e.g., architecture).
- Creating emotional connections and appreciation through learning with all senses.
- Impact- and practice-oriented learning, e.g., visits/internships at agricultural businesses, but the burden shouldn't fall solely on farmers. Educational programs and necessary investments may lead to more time and financial strain.
- Formulating long-term goals related to this.
- Broad awareness-raising efforts and measures to foster awareness.
- Information events by the City of Graz.
- Reducing legal barriers to food hygiene during practice-oriented learning (e.g., using collected herbs for snacks).
- Making information available through various sources to reach people with different backgrounds as comprehensively as possible (e.g., in supermarkets).
- The educational impact of direct marketing at farmers' markets and media support for such offers.
- Early education (starting at kindergarten level), where parents and educational institutions play a role.
- Parent education on quick and healthy recipes through communities and districts, while strengthening social networks and exchanges.
- Cross-disciplinary learning and food competence in school curricula (cooking lessons already exist in middle schools).
- Strengthening food competence across all age groups.
- The ability to transform knowledge from the digital sphere.
- Policy measures across multiple institutional levels to create a framework, e.g., limiting advertising.

2) Conservation of Natural Resources

- Using existing resources through platforms like Mundraub (which is interactive but requires funding for creation and maintenance).
- Linking nutrition and natural resources in people's awareness and promoting appropriate awareness-building.
- Intergenerational knowledge exchange.
- Offering information like the mushroom guide from the City of Graz and promoting such information more broadly.
- Regional media promotion of sustainable food production and the use of wild plants, etc.
- Education on available resources, like those offered by the Nature Conservation Association and Alpine Club.
- Utilizing the potential of technology and apps for information dissemination and education.
- Careful management of open spaces (City of Graz), which benefits all (flora, fauna, humans).
- Maintaining/creating green corridors and promoting public transportation to reduce conflicts with wildlife and private motorized vehicles.
- A shift in urban planning, moving away from redesigning spaces to integrating them.
- Long-term planning processes involving citizens, associations, and interest groups.
- Differentiating between graywater and drinking water in building codes.
- Reducing time as a limiting factor, to have the capacity to engage with and live sustainably.

3) Living Together in Diversity (Cultures, Generations, Social Groups, Inclusion)

- Free access to green spaces, edible plants, and arable land is important.
 - Access to arable land means empowerment—people can contribute their skills.
- Learning together: Diverse people bring diverse knowledge about growing and preparing useful plants (especially from other cultures). We want to learn together and from each other.
- Good organization of green spaces is essential (by the public sector). The detoxification of soils must also be considered (many soils in Graz contain toxins). Rules and a mediation office are needed for conflict resolution. We also need "caretakers."
- Individual vs. Collective: Will the spaces be jointly cultivated, or will plots, raised beds, and field sections be assigned to individuals (like mini-gardens or allotments), with additional communal areas?
- Mixed-use spaces: Combining green spaces with other uses like playgrounds (so parents can keep an eye on children), seating areas, etc.
- Intergenerational collaboration: Involving all generations so we can learn together and from each other. Slowing down is important here, as both the youngest and oldest generations often need more time.
- Edible city/green spaces as a second labor market: Connecting with social projects, similar to examples from cities like Andernach.

4) Biodiversity of Cultivated Plants, Wild Animals, and Wild Plants

- Using fallow land.
- Allowing/promoting rewilding (regulation needed, similar to the green space ordinance).
- Mowing less frequently.
- Wild shrub hedges (including edible ones).
- Spreading knowledge/information, including in private and educational sectors (schools, kindergartens, etc.).
- Animal-friendly architecture.
- Using heirloom plant varieties for climate change adaptation (e.g., for shading).
- Protecting trees—overhauling the tree protection ordinance.
- Leaving deadwood standing.
- Collecting water, creating biotopes.
- Promoting land de-sealing.
- Utilizing cemeteries.

5) Cross-sector Collaboration of Organizations

- An overview for associations and organizations, with regular meetings to get acquainted, exchange ideas, and plan joint activities.
- Awareness-raising for new forms of participation, so not just institutional representatives are involved but also affected individuals.
 - For example, in a neighborhood café or neighborhood planning—the perspective of the affected is often missing. How to involve them in urban planning (e.g., consulting the poverty network during planning processes)?
- Creating permanent advisory committees to bring NGO perspectives into design processes (e.g., food councils).
- Involving the poverty network: with external help, take the issue of food off the "waiting list" and build on it (Bachelor/Master's project?).
- How best to reach both young (digitally?!) and old (analog?!) generations.

6) Off-Topic Ideas:

- Poverty prevention: there's a need for recreational spaces, especially for those without a balcony—spaces free from consumption pressure.
 - Physical and mental well-being.
- Food literacy: How to communicate healthy eating and drinking?
- Healthy food isn't accepted!
- Snacks provided directly by the institution (school, kindergarten).
 - Free meals in schools—parents should still remain responsible.
 - Targeting children early with healthy eating habits.

- Gut health affects mental health and vice versa.
- For refugees: Create spaces for food production.
 - They often can only afford the "cheapest" food.
 - Especially children—inequality in school nutrition.

7) Gender Equality

- Stereotypes in:
 - Nutrition
 - Activities
 - Educational materials
 - Advertising
- Education:
 - Children
 - Men
 - Women
- *Women as caretakers**: Food, health, and biodiversity.
- What can be done for men?
 - Gardening
 - Cooking
- Quotas in decision-making bodies.
- Framework conditions for participatory processes.
- Involvement of businesses (e.g., gender equality plans).

8) Healthy Eating

- Key actors:
 - Associations (e.g., sports)
 - Childcare facilities
 - Schools → Health insurance, Styria Vitalis, medical nutrition counseling.
 - Universities and higher education institutions.
- Advertising:

- Influencers
- Public governance
- Framework conditions:
 - School cafeterias
 - Public institutions
 - Support policies: normative goals, market steering, alternative market strategies, taste education.
- Gradual transformation.
- Mainstreaming.
- Educational activities:
 - Traditional knowledge
 - Taste competence
 - Not socially selective
 - Contextualized knowledge generation
 - Nudging – goal setting.
 - Role models.
 - Unconventional/fun approaches.
 - Target group-specific contextualization.
 - Eating as a culturally and socially influenced act.
 - Breaking the rules: doing something different.
 - Curiosity, learning, and creating experiences.
 - Diverse competencies—drawing on different knowledge sources.
- Community festivals.

9) Participation in Urban Development Processes

- Involving diverse groups (at the neighborhood level).
- Identifying and recognizing (green) spaces owned by the city (potential guide).
- Insect-friendly areas ↔ Edible plants.
- Youth centers (for ideas and maintenance).
- Planting facades with vines in clean air.
- Digital feedback and comment opportunities for city design, with the city responding.

- Overview of city administration contact persons.
- Citizen science to identify plants and animals.
- Experts, kindergartens/primary schools.
- Participation exchange to connect people who want to garden ↔ facilitating garden projects.

10) Regional and Circular Economy

- Food production and composting in the city.
- Cheap leases for green spaces.
- Better waste sorting.
- Supporting startups.
- Better organic waste disposal options.
- Property management.
- Creating smaller, more manageable systems in food supply.
- Utilizing regional products (e.g., in canteens, with support from the city).
- **Limiting the number

ANNEX 3: List of ideas representing the BeSt concept from workshop 2

#	Name	Description
1	Creation and maintenance of edible landscapes within the framework of the second labor market	In the City of Graz, more areas will be designated as edible landscapes (fruit trees, herb/vegetable beds, raised beds). The harvesting opportunities will depend on the location (public spaces, housing estates). The establishment and maintenance will be carried out by a socio-economic enterprise (like in Andernach, Germany). This creates a win-win situation: this service can be offered at a lower cost, and people in the secondary job market will be employed in green jobs.
2	Increase in community gardens in settlements/housing estates	The few existing community gardens will be significantly increased in number. Gardens (raised beds, equipment, etc.) will be established in the city's residential buildings, cooperative housing, and private housing estates. The gardens will be tended by the residents – with guidance if necessary. There will be sufficient advisory services available. The gardens will be used for the cultivation of food and flowers.
3	Larger, unified funding scheme for edible city initiatives	A dedicated funding scheme for initiatives and projects as part of the "Edible City Graz" will be provided by the City of Graz. This fund can be used for purchases as well as for project financing. There will be different sub-funds for specific categories of gardens (community gardens, school gardens, therapeutic gardens, etc.). A portion will be allocated for economic startups. The process will work like a subsidy with prior application submission. Several requirements and target criteria must be met.
4	Low-threshold (educational) programs in various (social) institutions	A comprehensive, regular offering related to food and nutrition will be established in various institutions (community centres, youth centres, etc.) in Graz – available every day within a radius of XY km (~XY minutes on foot). <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Community cooking and eating, or meal distribution. • Workshops & consultations on healthy eating, gardening, etc. • Available informational materials. Some offerings are designed specifically for certain population groups, such as women*, but most are open to everyone. The food will be supplied by regional producers, with xy% of the food being organically produced..

5	Interdisciplinary education and practice-oriented learning in all school types & school gardens	<p>Gardens will become a part of every school in Graz. Where a school's grounds do not allow for the installation of a garden, there will be a nearby garden in public spaces that can be shared by several schools. The scale will be at least one garden bed per class.</p> <p>Elective subjects will emerge from optional courses, and there will also be interdisciplinary project-based lessons. Excursions to agricultural enterprises and nature hikes will be a fixed part of the school year. Students from low-income households will receive special support.</p>
6	Smaller, more straightforward options for organic waste disposal and composting	The number of organic waste bins will be reduced in favour of community-managed composting sites in the city. These will be connected to community gardens (Idea 2). Necessary resources, as well as training and consultation, will be provided.
7	Networking: regular meetings of various associations and organizations	Monthly networking meetings on the topics of "Edible City," "Food Sovereignty," and "Food Justice" will be held, to which everyone is invited. They serve as a platform for exchange and planning joint activities. A different host will invite attendees each time. This will form (part of) a Food Council.
8	Logistics through bike couriers	Urban food transportation will shift from trucks to bicycles. This will require, for example, micro-hubs, refrigerated bikes, the expansion of bike infrastructure, and appropriate digital infrastructure.
9	Creation of biotopes, allowing wild life growth (deadwood, animal-friendly architecture)	In Graz's green spaces and residential complexes, traditional lawns will be reduced. Animal-friendly architecture will be created, including deadwood corners and the establishment of new biotopes. These will be connected by corridors and will form part of the green network.
10	Goodbye to stereotypes	<p>In nutrition, advertising, and educational materials, there are stereotypical representations. These should be countered. To address this, a campaign will be developed in the City of Graz. Possible initiatives could include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A recipe book celebrating diversity • Social media activities • Educational and informational materials • "Anti-stereotype" advertising through the city's own communication channels
11	Use of platforms	In recent years, platforms related to the "edible city" have been established, such as mundraub.org or fruitmap.at in Graz. These platforms offer varying levels of information about plants and their locations. A new FruitMap is

		being developed for Graz as an information platform. It will make the edible city visible (via a map), provide professional background information, and include a forum for exchange. A participation board for gardens will also be established, as well as a platform for food sharing of garden produce.
12	Digital feedback options for urban planning	A new tool will be introduced that provides citizens with a low-barrier way to offer suggestions and proposals for urban design. Feedback from decision-makers will explain why something can or cannot be implemented.
13	Potential guide for usable green spaces	The potential of green spaces in Graz has not yet been fully tapped. Therefore, all areas will be examined in detail for various uses based on different criteria. A publicly accessible catalogue will be created.
14	Citizen science for identifying plants and animals	Citizen science projects offer a valuable opportunity to enhance the understanding and protection of biodiversity by bringing scientists and the general public together. The use of apps like iNaturalist, Pl@nt.net, and Flora Incognita will be promoted through these projects.

ANNEX 4: List of Examples for Leverage Points of the BeSt from workshop 3

Leverage Point	Example
Material: Constants, parameters, numbers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To promote the diversity of edible plants, a new tax on... The introduction of subsidies for community gardens would... An adjustment to pesticide limits could...
Material: Size of buffer stocks, relative to flows	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> By creating additional green spaces as buffer zones, it could... Increasing the city's seed reserves would... The introduction of rainwater storage in community gardens could...
Material: Structure of material stocks and flows	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A reorganization of supply chains for fresh food could... The establishment of central marketplaces for local products would... A well-connected system of community gardens and food centers can...
Processes: Length of delays, relative to rate of system change	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Accelerating the approval process for urban garden projects would... Shortening the waiting times for funding could... Faster dissemination of information about available cultivation areas would...
Processes: Strength of negative feedback loops	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Strict controls and sanctions for violations of cultivation regulations could... The introduction of a regular monitoring system for plant diversity would... Robust monitoring of water quality in urban gardens can...
Processes: Gain around positive feedback loops	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A reward system for citizens actively participating in community gardens could... The introduction of annual competitions for the best urban gardens would... A public recognition system for sustainable gardening projects can...
Design: Structure of information flows	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The creation of a central online portal for urban gardening initiatives would... Regular information events and workshops on plant diversity can... Better networking of the urban gardening communities could...
Design: Rules of the system (incentives, constraints)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> New municipal regulations to promote edible green spaces could... The introduction of mandatory training for urban gardeners would... Clear guidelines for the cultivation and maintenance of community gardens can...
Design: Power to change system structure or self-organize	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A municipal coordination office, hub, or "Edible City" competence center could... The use of climate-adapted varieties in the garden ecosystem helps... The reduction of redundant responsibilities leads to...
Intent: Goals of the system	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A new goal to establish the edible city as a model for sustainability would... Setting a goal for the maximum use of available urban spaces for

	<p>agriculture could...</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A goal to increase the city's self-sufficiency in fresh food can...
Intent: Paradigm underpinning the system	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A shift in thinking towards an edible city as the standard could... • Promoting a paradigm shift towards more citizen participation in urban planning would... • A new understanding of urban green spaces as primary food sources can...
Intent: Power to transcend paradigms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Openness to new approaches in urban agriculture could... • The willingness to question and change existing paradigms would... • A flexible attitude towards new ideas and experiments in urban planning can...

ANNEX 5: List of identified leverage points from workshop 3

Settlement community garden & biotops

Participants Ideas

Material Basis

- More resources: Availability of water, land, soil, nutrients, equipment
- More commitment & responsibility
- Fewer parking spaces
- More public outreach at the local level: low-barrier, e.g., district newspapers, event calendars
- More transparency through the publication of funds and budgets used
- More materials like seeds, tools, and wood
- Openness: few barriers in interacting with others
- More designated areas for shared use (proper lighting conditions)
- Clarification of financial basis
- Guidelines for limitations
- Social security

Processes

- Settlement guidelines, e.g., regarding which areas can be used for gardens and biotopes; which for other forms
- Designating responsible persons
- E.g., service offices for "living together"
- Designate areas for gardening
- Best practice examples
- Networking with other community gardens and gardeners
- Spaces – places for gardening, discussions, and celebrations
- Knowledge of decision-making processes
- Identification with decision processes
- Understanding natural processes, basic biological knowledge, permaculture
- Make finances transparent
- Pre-financing
- Deregulate retention basins and rivers as flood protection, preserve tree populations
- Division of labor based on talents
- Good spatial organization (honoring the 4 elements: fire, water, air, and earth)
- Workshops led by experts, accessible and held in neighborhood centers to motivate citizens
- Assign responsibility for various tasks

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Criteria for cultivation: organic methods, or use of self-grown seeds
<p>Structures</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Order + Time Organizational structure: Team: How is the team formed? How is it composed? Is it representative? Who decides what? Organizational structure: Starting point – formalize kickoff vs. guerrilla gardening Formation of an association or an open group Clarification of usage Clarification of responsibilities Accessibility - cross-cultural Working with all senses Safety for all actors: Comfort factor Botany lessons School gardens with guided tours Written rules for top-down and bottom-up approaches 	<p>Intention</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Vision + Motivation Graz Food and Agriculture Strategy Social & ecological component Dealing with resistance and defensiveness Top down vs. bottom up Multigenerational work connects Inclusiveness Children learn to feel the earth again + work with it Involve the neighborhood: Promote community Practice democracy Bind CO2 Climate adaptation With what ease is what type of space used? Less individualism Who owns the community garden? New land in a familiar environment Processes: Dealing with resistance and defensiveness Know strategies and integrate them

Education & School Garden

Participants Ideas

Material Base <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Restriction – not possible at all schools• Budget: Parent Association• Integration into the curriculum• Inspiration and motivation for both young and old• Many schools have been trying their hand at school gardens – for years?• Large groups	Processes <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Parent Association & School Social Work.• Primary School: Can be integrated into every subject.• Secondary School: Interdisciplinary work.• Community orientation: Ethics and Eco-Social.• Purchasing, borrowing, and sharing of resources.
Structures <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Safety• Integration of local businesses• Afternoon care (recreational supervisors → school gardens)• Organization of the timetable• Organization of garden supervision in summer• Organization of access to water• Working with all senses	Intention <ul style="list-style-type: none">• School garden = new territory → peer exchange• Name responsible individuals• Interdisciplinary• Life cycle of plants• Interaction of living beings

ANNEX 6: List of identified impacts for broader change from workshop 4

Impact on system	Impact description
Living together (Social)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strengthening belonging and being at home • Violence and Vandalism Prevention • Increasing the sense of self-efficacy as a prevention of radicalization • Goods or service offerings as offers for the secondary labor market • Increased identification with the district/"Grätzl"
Culture	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create spaces that can also be used for communal activities by others • Cultural and social exchange on equal terms within the framework of shared interests
Education	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promotion of knowledge about nature • Workshops on Sustainable Nutrition and Gardening • Children but also adults less meat more fruit + vegetables • make global sustainability issues tangible locally • Spaces for Co-Creative Sustainability Education • Accessibility for low-threshold educational offers
Needs of specific groups (Inclusion, Intersectionality)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • People with a migration background experience an enhancement due to their high gardening know-how • Empowerment & social participation for disadvantaged population groups • Promotion of healthier eating for larger families through access to cultivation land • increased self-efficacy -> improvement of one's own living environment
Nature (Flora, Fauna, Water, etc.)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nature-friendly management. -> Habitat for animals & plants -> Promotes biodiversity. • Soil + Species - Protection • Biodiversity + healthy soils • Natural hospitality • Steppingstone biotopes • Green space protection (Flood protection)

Health	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promotion of self-cooking through home-grown fruits + vegetables • Bio- Healthy- Food for everyone • Health promotion through togetherness • Sharing knowledge of nature • No use of pesticides + chemical fertilizers • Fresh food nutritional quality • Improved health competence / increased resilience
Urban Development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Upgrading measures for areas • quick acquaintance with the roommates in urban development areas through garden events • conscious intervention in troubled neighbourhoods
Work, Economy & Tourism	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New Professional Profiles, e.g. Climate Gardener "Green Jobs"